

METHODS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY

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Abstract: This scientific article is dedicated to help readers to make teaching more effective, by learning worthwhile methods and the inner mental and by then understanding how classroom activities and teacher decisions can create, or limit, children's opportunities for learning.

Key words: Globalization, communicative language teaching (CLT), flipped classroom, gamification method, audiolingual method, the silent way (SW), cognates, eclectic approach.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization emphasizes the growing importance of English as a language of international communication. Learning foreign language has its own challenges and barriers. However, practising teachers should overcome these challenges by worthwhile methods and techniques. As well as, language acquisition is a complicated process including several factors and that this process is incredibly influenced due to the flexibility of the brain. This article explores using 7 methods to teach English.

Communicative language teaching (clt)

This approach is probably the most popular teaching model globally for teaching English right now. Partly because it focuses on putting students in a variety of real-life situations so they can learn how to use language skills to communicate in the real world. Therefore, teachers focus on fluency of communication rather than accuracy, and lessons are practical rather than theoretical. That's why many scientists today prefer communication. Even if he cannot speak correctly, the important thing is to convey his opinion.

Flipped classroom

The flipped classroom technique of modern teaching involves students learning new material or content independently at home and then practicing the material at school - replacing the usual school homework. This method gives students more time to understand the topics, while ensuring they get the help they need in class to get their questions answered. This method shows a 50% positive result.

Gamification method

Kids love games, and modern teaching methods help create a new and more effective learning environment where children can learn and have fun at the same time. Game techniques help to motivate students, make them interested in learning. New skills help develop their critical thinking skills. For example, you can ask the vocabulary related to the topic by the snowball method. According to the method, each student writes one new word to a piece of paper and folds it like a snowflake. Then throw them to each other. The student hit by the snowball should say the translation of the word in the paper. At that time, students feel as they are playing a real snowball.

Grammar and translation method

The method of Grammar and Translation is one of the oldest methods of teaching foreign languages, being widely used in Europe in the 19th century.

The first step of this method is the presentation of grammar rules. You should learn grammar rules for formulating sentences step by step. The rules are then applied in text translation and analysis exercises, where students have the opportunity to practice and internalize the knowledge.

The next step of the method is the translation of texts. Students are exposed to authentic texts in the foreign language and then translate these texts into their mother tongue. Translation helps to develop the ability to understand and interpret texts, in addition to contributing to the acquisition of vocabulary.

Nowadays the Grammar and Translation method has been criticized by some experts because this method demand more time and it is boring. Experts argue that the method does not develop communicative skills, such as fluency and listening. However, it helps to enhance reading and writing skills. In addition, the method continues to be used in some schools and universities around the world.

Audiolingual method

Audiolingual method is one of the most popular methods in the world. This method has been used since the 1950s and 1960s. Repetition, memorization and intensive practice of the language being studied are emphasized using oral and listening exercises to develop communicative skills.

The audiolingual method is also useful for students who want to learn a foreign language for specific purposes, such as travel or business. It can help develop practical and situational communicative skills, such as making reservations at a hotel. However, the audiolingual method has some limitations. First of all, it does not emphasize the development of reading comprehension or grammar.

The silent way (sw)

The Silent Way is the name of a language teaching method developed by Caleb Gattegno. It is based on the premise that the teacher should be as quiet as possible in the classroom, but students should explore and deduce the language rules themselves. This method can be expressed as follows:

- Learning is facilitated if the learner discovers or creates rather than remembers and repeats what is to be learned.
- Learning is facilitated by accompanying (mediating) physical objects.
- Learning is facilitated by problem solving involving the material to be learned.

Teacher should tell one of the students that he has to teach a theme to his coursemates. If teacher use the silent method more during the lesson, students will be more independent learners.

Cognates

Students are taught to recognize cognates by studying matching spelling or sound patterns between languages. Students are also asked to remember words that look like cognate words but have different meanings in the target language than in their mother tongue. This method is of course only useful for similar languages. Such as English and Spanish languages.

ENGLISH	SPANISH
family	familia
center	centro
desert	desierto
magic	magia

CONCLUSION

Each of the above approaches has its own pros and cons, and no one method is universally regarded as superior to the others in all teaching contexts. Establishing a positive and supportive atmosphere, clear expectations and routines, supportive teacher-student relationships, cooperative learning, and safe communication environments are among necessary to promote an optimal learning environment. The importance of creating positive teacher-student relationships cannot be overstated, as these relationships form the basis of a confident and nurturing classroom atmosphere.

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